

EXPERIMENTAL PRACTICES IN CHEMISTRY THROUGH TIKTOK TECHNOLOGY AND MEDIA LANGUAGE : EXPERIENCE REPORT WITH A GROUP OF STUDENTS IN THE 1ST YEAR OF THE NEW HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to describe the importance of experimental practices for chemistry classes and the verbal, gestural and media expression of students through feedback through the TikTok media platform. Developed by a professor of Chemistry, inserted in the teaching staff of a State College, in the north of Paraná, in the Elective Curricular Component of Chemistry. This component was named "Chemistry TikTok", in which the participants were full-time 1st Year A and B students of New High School. To develop the present work, it was defined: objectives, abilities and competences to be advanced, syllabus contents, methodology, didactic resources, proposal for the culmination and finally the evaluation. The results of the present study show that to develop this work with the students of the 1st Year of the New High School of Full Time there were many difficulties, mainly with the behavior of some students, as they were not actively involved in the proposed activities. Promising aspects for learning are highlighted, even though not having posted as many videos as they produced, it is noted that with each class

that passed, the students' interest increased, as they wanted to do more and more experiments, record videos, actively participate in them, demonstrating greater mastery of the chemical concepts worked.

Keywords: Chemistry teaching; Experimental classes; TikTok media platform.

1. INTRODUCTION

Experimental practices in chemistry are fundamental for students' meaningful learning, uniting theory and practice. Through practical classes, students can understand the scientific concepts worked in the classroom, how chemistry is built and developed, testing the theory through laboratory experiments (RIBEIRO, 2018).

Chemistry is a very challenging science and at school it is often out of context with the reality of students and thus, they are unable to associate learning with their daily life. The National Curriculum Parameters address this decontextualization: In Brazil, the approach to school Chemistry remains practically the same, although sometimes “made up” with an appearance of modernity, the essence remains the same, prioritizing information disconnected from the reality experienced by students and by teachers (BRASIL, 1999, p. 30).

Given the above, meaningful learning becomes important since it is carried out from the pre-existing concepts arising from the student. The teacher must establish a dialogue with the students in order to make teaching more relevant and meaningful for them (GIFFONI, 2019).

Experimentation in Chemistry Teaching is of fundamental importance, because through this method the students' difficulties in understanding the contents of chemistry can be overcome, making the study more pleasurable and contributing to the increase of scientific knowledge applied in the student's daily life (SALESSE, 2012).

Through experimental practice, the theoretically worked content starts to make sense to the student and so they can interact more with the concepts of chemistry, solve problem situations, carry out research of various experiments, according to their curiosities. Giordan (1999) found that experimentation awakens a strong interest among students, who attribute to it a motivating, playful nature and essentially linked to the senses.

Laboratory classes are fundamental for the student to have a meaningful learning experience, since this methodology allows the student to experience the construction, development and reactions of chemistry (SALESSE, 2012). Practical activities play a crucial role in the development of playfulness and it is an effective strategy in the teaching-learning process, since practical classes in chemistry teaching favor the construction of concepts that

encompass it, such as handling and transforming substances as well as the theoretical explanation of the phenomena that occurred (SANTOS; MENEZES, 2020).

In this way, experimental practices need to be inserted in the teaching/learning methodologies of the teacher, as it will result not only in theoretical learning, but also in practical learning, giving students the opportunity to manipulate laboratory instruments, awakening interest in scientific research, thus making students protagonists of their own knowledge.

This article aims to describe the importance of experimental practices for chemistry classes and the verbal, gestural, and media expression of students through feedback through the TikTok media platform .

This is a qualitative research, an experience report developed by a Chemistry teacher, inserted in the teaching staff of a State College in western Paraná, in the Elective Curricular Component of Chemistry. This component was named “Chemistry TikTok”, in which the participants were full-time 1st Year A and B students of New High School. The class was made up of 40 students, half from Class A and half from Class B, under the guidance and supervision of the area coordinator, who is also the author of this article.

2 TIKTOK AS A FORM OF LANGUAGE

TikTok is one of the Digital Technologies that provides students with a form of language through facial, gestural and audiovisual expressions, providing information on a particular topic. This media is part of the daily life of this generation of students and why not bring it to the classroom. Monteiro (2020) states that TikTok can be used not only for fun, but also for the distribution of creative content, for student integration and the development of their creative potential, as well as a learning assessment tool.

When working with this TikTok tool, teachers and students can actively interact in the classroom and experiment labs, where those involved have the opportunity to expose their acquired knowledge and publish their practical work to the community. In this way, they play an investigative role to select the best experiments to be presented and posted on TikTok .

This digital methodology has been promising for teaching chemistry, because it allows interaction between theory and practice and works as an important didactic resource for learning concepts considered difficult for students to understand.

Through TikTok, students can record short videos and share them on social networks, so they will be acquiring new knowledge in a fun way. Costa et. Al. (2012) emphasizes the use

of digital cameras, or in this case, smartphones that offer countless possibilities in the classroom.

Currently, the digital world is present daily in the social life of citizens, we live in an era of media generation, where little is said personally, communications are mostly through the media.

As a result of the advancement and multiplication of information and communication technologies and the increasing access to them due to the greater availability of computers, cell phones, tablets and the like, students are dynamically inserted in this culture, not only as consumers. Young people have increasingly engaged as protagonists of digital culture, getting directly involved in new forms of multimedia and multimodal interaction and social networking, which are carried out in an increasingly agile way.(BRASIL, 2018, p. 63).

Faced with these demands and educational needs, this work was developed in order to promote learning of Chemistry concepts in students of the 1st Year of New High School.

3 METHODOLOGY

This is an experience report, developed by a Chemistry teacher, inserted in the teaching staff of a State College in western Paraná, in the Elective Curricular Component of Chemistry. This component was named “Chemistry TikTok”, in which the participants were full-time 1st Year A and B students of New High School. The class was made up of 40 students, half from Class A and half from Class B, under the guidance and supervision of the area coordinator, who is also the author of this article.

To develop this work, it was defined: objectives, skills and competences to be developed, syllabus contents, methodology, didactic resources, proposal for the culmination and end of the evaluation, as described respectively below.

General Purpose : To describe the importance of experimental practices for chemistry classes and the verbal, gestural, and media expression of students through feedback through the TikTok media platform . Through this elective, the student will be able to be the protagonist of his own knowledge, in it, an experimental practice of chemistry will be presented in all meetings, always related to the content worked in the classroom. In addition, the class will be encouraged to research new experiments related to the day's content and in the next classes will record their presentations, to later be posted on a TikTok account created by them, with the help of the professor/adviser, who will use the @ da school, for reasons of posting responsibility, being posted only experiments oriented in the laboratory and with total security. In this way,

all knowledge acquired will be shared with other students and the community that view TikTok . This elective was also designed for the return to face-to-face classes, trying to remedy all educational damage related to natural sciences, which the student had during a pandemic.

Specific objectives of the activity : To enable the student to be the protagonist of his own knowledge; Develop a critical attitude to analyze the importance of chemistry in your school and social life; Recognize the importance of empathy, listening and dialogue in situations involving teamwork; Develop technological skills, recordings, internet research, video editing and posting on social networks; Develop responsibilities for safety in the chemistry laboratory, without taking risks of accidents; Know all the laboratory glassware, name and function of each one of them; Develop commitment to the functions required for the development of the project: experiment research, organization of reagents to be used, date of presentation, editing and posting of videos.

Skills and Competencies to be developed: Scientific Research, mediation, determination, creativity, self-control, self-knowledge, empathy, curiosity, motivation, respect, care, collaboration in group activities and responsibility.

Contents: Simple and compound substances, homogeneous and heterogeneous mixtures, solutions, chemical reaction, density, volume, temperature, exothermic and endothermic reactions.

Methodology: We use two weekly classes always on Thursdays from 12:50 to 14:30. In the weekly Chemistry classes that precede the Elective, the teacher presented the experiment and as a task the students carried out a research of other experiments related to the studied content. The proposal is that this task should always be carried out in a group and should be presented in the chemistry laboratory in the following classes of the elective. It is intended to use four fifty-minute classes for each content. Each group will have a student responsible for recording the experimental practice presented by the group, who will be the group leader.

Didactic resources: Chemistry laboratory, computer science, digital whiteboard, cell phone, notebook and textbook.

Proposal for the culmination: On the culmination day that occurred at the end of the school year, all students presented an experimental practice chosen by the group. This presentation of the practices was carried out for the other students of the school and for the visiting students of the 9th grade from another school in the municipality who, naturally, would make up the 1st grade classes of this school the following year. (who tend to be the future students of this college in which our research was applied). Also, the TikTok account was presented, with all the recordings made by the students throughout the year. And, at the end, a

video was shown with the recording errors, so that the other students of the school and visitors could perceive how the work of the students was in this elective, during the year and that, in the face of errors and successes, our works were developed, successfully, fun and many attempts.

Assessment: Of the formative type, in which each student was assessed for their performance, skills and competences, individual and collective participation, development of practices, research and presentations of the activities carried out.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the first week of class, teachers presented all the electives that would be available for that year of studies, and students, in a democratic way, were able to choose their electives. Class already defined, on the first day of the class, it was explained to the students how the dynamics of the Chemistry TikTok, they were asked to create a profile on TikTok, with the name 'Chemistry TikTok Elective', with the email @escola, in which they should post a video produced by them during the chemistry experiments, as they would be the protagonists of all works. They were organized into groups: research group, experiment recording group and editing and posting group on the social network they created.

Several experiments were carried out during the school year on the contents: Simple and compound substances, homogeneous and heterogeneous mixtures, solutions, laboratory glassware; chemical reaction, density, volume, temperature, exothermic and endothermic reactions. For this research, we will highlight only two experiments, which were presented on the day of the culmination: exothermic reactions (caustic soda and aluminum) and laboratory glassware.

The research group always posted the investigated experiments in a whatsapp group in advance, so that the teacher and students could organize themselves in the theoretical/practical explanation of the experiment. At the time of the classes, the students organized the laboratory benches, with all the glassware, equipment and reagents, after everything was organized, the recording attempts began, as they got nervous, got the lines wrong and had to return, but they always managed to record an explanatory video.

Students in the Chemistry TikTok elective showed off their work at the end of the school year at an event at the high school called "culmination". Since each elective had only thirty minutes to present, the groups selected two experiments to demonstrate, as follows:

Experiment 1: Chemical Reactions

Objectives of this experiment: demonstrate the occurrence of an exothermic chemical reaction, demonstrate the formation of new products and collect hydrogen gas.

To develop such an experiment was used as reagents: Sodium hydroxide, water and aluminum. During the experiment, the students were able to observe the formation of new products, sodium aluminate (NaAlO_2) and hydrogen gas (H_2).

Represented by the following chemical equation:

Through this experiment, the students learned what an exothermic reaction is (emits heat), the formation of hydrogen gas and, they had the experience of collecting the gas in a bladder and shortly after exploding the balloon to show the existence of the gas. It was an activity that caught their attention, as they demonstrated to be involved in the process and reported having enjoyed it a lot, as they learned the content.

Figure 1: chemical reactions

Source: the authors

Experiment 2: Laboratory glassware

After the chemical reaction experiment, the students presented some glassware and equipment and their role in laboratory activities. The purpose of the presentation would be to show the main types of glassware used in scientific experiments, their characteristics, functions

and care required for proper handling without risk. According to Salesse (2012), experimentation is a way to bring students closer to the reality of chemistry, stimulating interest, curiosity and the pursuit of scientific knowledge. In addition, experimentation makes chemical studies more enjoyable and meaningful, as it allows students to relate theory to practice. In this “TikTok da Química” work, the experiments carried out by the students can be considered as a pedagogical strategy that favors learning and raising awareness about the importance of care when handling reagents and laboratory equipment.

Figure 2: Laboratory glassware

Source: the authors

Chemistry's TikTok media platform

One of the interesting aspects of the "TikTok of Chemistry " elective was the posting of videos of experiments developed by the protagonist students on the video platform "TikTok of Chemistry". Even though they did not publish many experiments, this action allowed the students to share the recordings of the experiments, which they carried out during the elective classes, showing the results, procedures and scientific explanations behind each experimental activity, in addition to disseminating chemical knowledge to a wide and diverse audience, students were also able to develop communication skills , creativity and collaboration, using technological resources and various languages.

In addition to the benefits mentioned above, it is worth mentioning that the students' verbal and media expression was greatly stimulated through this activity, since they needed to put this skill into practice when presenting and explaining the experiments to their colleagues and, when preparing the material for post on the TikTok platform . Such activity meets the BNCC with regard to general competence 5:

“Understand, use and create digital information and communication technologies in a critical, meaningful, reflective and ethical way in the various social practices (including school ones) to communicate, access and disseminate information, produce knowledge, solve problems and exercise protagonism and authorship in personal and collective life. (BRASIL, 2018. 11).

TiTok Chemistry elective classes , highlighted the importance of understanding, using and creating digital information and communication technologies in a critical, creative, meaningful, reflective and ethical way. This general competence 5 of the BNCC is essential for students to be able to communicate, access and share information, produce knowledge, solve problems, have autonomy and initiative, in addition to developing collective cooperation skills. By using the TikTok platform to publicize the experiments, students were able to explore different languages, resources and media formats, in addition to interacting with other users and receiving feedback. In this way, they developed cognitive, socio-emotional and digital skills that are essential for the 21st century.

SOME CONSIDERATIONS

The present study is concluded emphasizing that to develop this work with the students of the 1st year of the new High School of Full Time, of a state school of the public net North of Paraná. During the first classes of the “TikTok of Chemistry” elective, there were many difficulties, mainly with the behavior of some students, as they were not actively involved in the proposed activities, many of them were in the way all the time with jokes, side conversations, without commitments and did not do anything, what was assigned to them by the group, they didn't record responsibly, they didn't edit the videos in the required time or they refused to do the proposed activity.

However, even in the face of the difficulties presented by the participants, potential aspects regarding the learning of these students must be highlighted, since, even though they did not post as many videos as they produced, it is noted that, with each class that passed, their interest increased, because they wanted to do more and more experiments. Therefore, in this work, it was verified that the use of TikTok in experimental chemistry classes provided moments of fun for students. In addition, these students, who were previously unmotivated by the classes, began to interact with each other. This is in line with what Monteiro (2020) states, that TikTok information and communication technology engages students as protagonists of digital culture. This idea also confirms the statement by Brazil (2018), which highlights the importance of integrating digital technologies in education.

It is considered that this activity with the media language was of great value in teaching and learning Chemistry, and it is important to point out that in her statement the teacher stated that “if it had happened with *smaller groups of students, perhaps the experience would have been more successful*”, a reflection she made, based on the difficulties in managing a large group of students in more interactive classes, which require greater teaching attention in order to manage the demands of students and act in mediating them with the scientific knowledge on the agenda, was a challenge when proposing this type of didactic instrument.

Therefore, even with the difficulties of developing activities of this type and in the case of a public school, where teaching resources are not always adequate, it is still necessary for teachers to invest in diversified methodologies, so that they can encourage their students to arouse greater interest in the scientific content taught in classes that are configured as theoretical/practical.

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